

Beliefs and Practices of Senior High School Teachers and College Instructors on Intercultural Communicative Competence

Zayda S. Asuncion, Rosalie L. Navoa, Maria Ines R. Minia & Marites B. Querol

Abstract

This study tries to address quality assurance among teachers/instructors/mentors of the topic *intercultural competence* in the subjects Oral Communication (OC) in the Senior High School and Purposive Communication (PC) in the university level. The study aimed to answer the following questions: (1) What are the beliefs and practices of teachers/instructors/ professors on: (a) the objectives of Second Language Teaching (SLT), (b) the Components of Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) for Language Learners in the Philippines and (c) their beliefs regarding Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) in Classroom Teaching?; (2) How frequent do the teachers (a) include the topics in ICC in their classes (Oral Communication or Purposive Communication), (b) utilize the activities in their classes?; (3) Do the teachers/instructors/professors' beliefs in intercultural competence relate to their (a) practices in teaching intercultural communicative competence and (b) profile?; and (3) Is there a difference between the ICC of the teachers when they are grouped according to their classification? The study included 17 teachers (9 from the SHS and 8 from the tertiary) who were purposively chosen. An ICC questionnaire (adapted from Tian, 2013) was used to gather the teachers' responses regarding ICC after getting their consent. The results indicate that the teachers are generally the same in their beliefs and practices on ICC and both consider the objectives and components of ICC important. The belief on the importance of language proficiency correlated with four ICC topics and the belief on the relevance of students' attitudes correlated with three activities in ICC. As regards profile, age, gender and years of teaching correlated with some ICC activities. When tested for significant difference, the two groups differed only in one, i.e., in focusing on the students' attitudes of openness and tolerance towards other peoples and cultures in which the SHS gained a higher mean.

Keywords: *Intercultural Communicative competence, K12, Oral Communication, Purposive Communication*

Introduction

The advent of K12 curriculum that addresses the needs of the Filipino students identified by the government for ASEAN integration resulted in a number of challenges to the Filipinos. Specifically, the teachers of the two new levels in the secondary level, senior high school, need to cope with new subjects and new topics. The teachers of English specifically of *Oral Communication (OC)* need to address a number of competencies in which one is *intercultural communicative competence (ICC)*. In the same way, the faculty of higher education are also undergoing a similar challenge to address the needs of the college students as a result of K12. In response to the CHED Memo no. 20, s.2013 that provides for the creation of the New General Education (GE) courses in the tertiary level in which one theoretical outcome is "knowing the self, Filipino society, the world, and the environment, and how these intersect" (Cruz, 2014, par 6), the subject Purposive Communication (PC) was created as one of the GE courses. PC includes the topic *intercultural communicative competence (ICC)* which is one thrust in education and in English language teaching (ELT). "In the context of globalization, intercultural teaching has been suggested as an objective in English as lingua franca (ELF) education, which has challenged English teachers in acquiring the intercultural communicative competence (ICC) [also known as *intercultural competence (IC)*] in English language teaching (ELT)" (Han & Song, 2011; Luk, 2012; Sercu, 2006 in Tzu-Chia, 2016, p. 71). Byram (1997) and Spencer-Oatey and Franklin (2009) "have suggested that IC [ICC] be adequately developed to ensure that people from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds can interact appropriately and effectively with each other". Intercultural communicative competence (IC) described as "the ability to communicate in international settings effectively and appropriately through awareness of differences in one's own and others' culture" is considered critical in the global milieu (Jantadej & Charubus, 2018, p. 39; Zhang & Zhang, 2015). Further, Jantadej and Charubus claimed that IC needs to be directly and continually taught to learners. However, as Tian (2013) mentioned in her study on ICC, the literature is scarce on its discussion of the eastern and western views on the similarity and differences of cultures. This study could provide enlightenment on the gap as it aims to investigate

aspects of ICC in English as a second language (ESL) in the Philippines. Having a baseline data on intercultural communicative competence (ICC) from Filipino faculty members who are directly teaching it does not only mean providing answer to the query on the possible similarities or differences of cultures but could also mean a breakthrough in the implementation of k12 curriculum and in providing for the institutional responsibility of quality assurance. The data could provide a number of information as regards the strengths and weaknesses of mentors of IC, and it could serve as a source of information to upgrade the teaching of the two subjects and to provide necessary assistance to the teachers.

The study addresses the need for quality teaching in the two subjects in English, Oral Communication in the senior high school and Purposive Communication in the tertiary level by identifying the beliefs and practices of teachers/instructors/professors on intercultural communication.

Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions: (1) What are the beliefs and practices of teachers/instructors/professors on: (a) the objectives of Second Language Teaching (SLT), (b) the Components of Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) for Language Learners in the Philippines and (c) their beliefs regarding Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) in Classroom Teaching; (2) How frequent do the teachers (a) include the topics in ICC in their classes (Oral Communication or Purposive Communication), (b) utilize the activities in their classes? (3) Do the teachers/instructors/professors' beliefs in intercultural competence relate to their (a) practices in teaching intercultural communicative competence and (b) profile?; and (3) Is there a difference between the ICC of the teachers when they are grouped according to their classification?

For several decades, the concept of native-speaker competence in language teaching has influenced the paradigm of English language teaching (ELT) even after Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) was introduced. Even with CLT, an argument on its inadequacy in language teaching has been posed by a number of educators and linguists. They claim that the present view of language development has underrated the importance of culture despite the unfailing action of many to attract consciousness on the importance of culture in language teaching (Stern, 1992 in Corbett, 2003). However, recently, efforts to incorporate culture in CLT have been observed; hence, the introduction of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) or intercultural competence (IC). This does not change, however, the basic goal of CLT which is communicative competence. Rather, IC is an extension or expansion in that communicators need to address the issue of culture in any communicative event. "Moreover, as learners come to a deeper understanding of how the target language is used to achieve the explicit and implicit cultural goals of the [target] language community, they should be prompted to reflect on the ways in which their own language and community functions. The intercultural learner ultimately serves as a mediator between different social groups that use different languages and language varieties" (Corbett, 2003, p.2). With this view, the ultimate goal of language education has shifted from 'native speaker competence' to 'intercultural communicative competence' (Byram, 1977). According to Corbett, the integration of IC in language education trains the language learner to "view different cultures from a perspective of informed understanding" (p.2). One's cultural knowledge enables him or her to communicate more appropriately which must result in a more effective communication. After all, multiculturalism is a natural phenomenon that must not be taken for granted.

Byram (1997) described intercultural communication in relation to the intercultural speaker. When interlocutors come from varied countries, regions or communities meet, they bring with them their unique backgrounds that can affect the current communication situation. Their knowledge could be substantial or minimal as needed in the communicative event. Hence, it is important to ensure that the interlocutors arrive at substantial knowledge that is needed for effective communication to occur in the communication situation. For teachers and students, the teachers of intercultural communication need the desired knowledge or beliefs in order to communicate these concepts to students. This IC knowledge of teachers could be translated in their practices in the ICC class. Hence, the teachers' knowledge or beliefs and their practices manifesting their abilities and skills on ICC are critical.

The results of the study will be used as basis to conduct seminars/workshops on IC to the two groups of teachers. This would affirm the teachers' positive beliefs and best practices on IC. At the same time, it could be a venue for further clarification of doubts on ICC and for sharing of the good or best practices of the teachers on ICC. This study is guided by the following paradigm:

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

The teacher remains the key figure in the classroom though the focus is the learner. In order to provide for the needs of the learner, it is presupposed that the teacher must be competent in his/her field of specialization or area of knowledge. As regards, English language teaching in the Philippines, specifically in the senior high school and in the tertiary level, the teacher's competence in IC as manifested in his or her beliefs and practices could render a number of pedagogical implications. The beliefs of the mentor on intercultural competence which could be based on three aspects: beliefs as to what the objectives of ESL teaching are, beliefs on the components of IC for learners, and beliefs regarding IC in classroom teaching could have a direct relationship or influence on the teaching practices of the teacher. The practices could be measured based on the teacher's inclusion of topics that are considered representations of intercultural competence and based on the activities provided in the class. Ascertaining the teachers' beliefs could provide the institution and the learners confidence on the provision of quality teaching. However, the teachers' beliefs on IC may not necessarily relate to or be reflected in his/her practices in teaching IC. Thus, a number of pedagogical implications can be derived from the beliefs and practices of the teacher or professor on intercultural competence.

The present study only involved the seventeen English mentors in the senior high school (9 teachers) and tertiary level (8 instructors) of SMU Bayombong. It did not include other teachers in the university. The study was limited to participants' beliefs and practices on intercultural communication as a part of their language classes as reflected in the items in the questionnaire and interview guide. Other implications of culture are not included in this study.

The study will provide baseline data on the knowledge and competence of the senior high school and the college mentors in English regarding intercultural communicative competence to ensure quality teaching in the two subjects, Oral Communication and Purposive Communication. The study therefore provides for quality assurance in the service of the students enrolled in the two subjects since the topic is a necessary life skill in the present global milieu. It may also be classified under wellness in SMU project WEALTH.

Further, "[e]ven if students never speak the language [they have learned] after leaving school, for a lifetime they will retain the cross-cultural skills and knowledge, the insight, and the access to a world beyond traditional borders." (*Standards for Foreign Language Learning*, 1996: 24 cited in Byram, 1997).

Several studies all over the world have ventured on establishing the relationship between language and culture (Canale & Swain, 1980; Byram, Morgan, et al. 1994; Crozet & Liddicot, 2000 in Nguyen, 2015). All these studies argue that language and culture are interdependent and the kind of relationship that exists between the two is interactive. Hence, one is inseparable from the other. Kramersch (1995, also in Nguyen, 2015) posits that understanding the culture that surrounds the language is considered a skill after listening, speaking, reading, and writing. McKay (2000) also argues that language learning is culture learning. One will find it difficult to communicate with other people without understanding the cultures that they belong to. As Bennett, Bennett and Allen (2003) put it "the person who learns language without learning culture risks becoming a fluent fool" (p. 237) (Bennett, Bennett, & Allen, 2003, p. 237).

In language teaching, experts have introduced an array of pedagogical approaches with their corresponding strength. For instance, In the 1970s, Hymes introduced Communicative Competence as an approach to language teaching with emphasis on linguistic competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence, strategic competence, and pragmatic competence. Hence, communicative competence became the main goal of every language learner. However, several scholars criticized this approach because it does not include cultural competence (Nguyen, 2015). Thus, Byram (1997) has refocused language teaching with emphasis on culture as the core of language education. Accordingly, intercultural competence is a term that reflects the principle that the culture of the learner is as relevant as the foreign culture (Kramersch, 1993, in Nguyen, 2015).

Several definitions have emerged about intercultural competence. For one, Byram (1997) considers it as the ability to communicate and interact across cultural boundaries. Paige et al. (2004) regard it as “one’s ability to interact and communicate effectively with persons from other cultures and in culturally diverse settings” (p.79). Another definition comes from Deardoff (2006) who states that intercultural competence is “the ability to communicate effectively and appropriately in intercultural situations based on one’s intercultural knowledge, skills and attitudes” (p. 194). Song, (2009, in Zhang & Zhang, 2015) defines intercultural competence as “a person’s ability to engage in productive intercultural dialogues of meanings and relationships with people from different cultural backgrounds” (p. 56).

Based on these notions of intercultural competence, several research enthusiasts have conducted studies on this area in relation to English as a Foreign Language teaching. Intercultural competence studies on ESL teaching however is scant.

Gu (2015) surveyed the opinions and attitudes of Chinese EFL teachers towards intercultural communicative competence. Results showed that the Chinese EFL teachers showed limited knowledge of ICC but they were willing to assess the intercultural communicative competence of their learners. The findings imply the confusion of the respondents in relation to what to assess and how to assess it. The problem was caused mainly by the teachers’ lack of knowledge on ICC and language learning, lack of administrative support, and lack of available resources for material development.

The study of Chao (2016) focused on identifying the intercultural communication competence of 455 Taiwanese ELT teachers with the use of a self-assessment inventory and interview. Results revealed that most of the Taiwanese ELT teachers had positive attitudes toward intercultural communication. In addition, the respondents considered themselves skillful in intercultural communication but they admitted that they lacked competence on the non-verbal aspects of other cultures. As regards the perspectives of the respondents about the goals, models and materials of ELT, many of them did not consider the need of related topics on English as a Lingua Franca or as an international language. To some, cultural learning was not as relevant as acquiring language ability. They preferred to integrate the culture of the English native speakers over other cultures in ELT and they were more inclined to use the materials developed by native speakers of English. The participants also admitted that they sometimes employed traditional strategies to integrate culture in ELT.

Zhou (2011) ventured on identifying the Chinese EFL teachers’ intercultural competence, their beliefs about the objectives of EFL education. Based on a survey questionnaire, the Chinese EFL teachers demonstrated an average intercultural competence with attitudes as the highest and knowledge as the lowest of the four dimensions. Moreover, the respondents considered linguistic dimension of teaching more important than cultural dimension. Nevertheless, they found the objectives for promoting intercultural competence of students important. The teachers also manifested positive attitude toward the integration of cultures of English-speaking countries to EFL teaching.

In Vietnam, Nguyen, T. (2015) determined the Vietnamese EFL teachers’ perception of intercultural competence, their role in promoting intercultural competence in the EFL classroom, and their practice of integrating intercultural competence in their classrooms. Results showed that the teacher participants showed less support to the objective of developing intercultural competence of learners as compared to the development of their language competence. As to the cultural aspect of language teaching, the respondents were more interested to the development of cultural knowledge and skills of learners than they were in the development of learners’ attitudes. They also disclosed that they integrated activities such as the use of videos and the internet to teach foreign cultures to their students. They too exhibited positive attitude towards the importance of cultural aspects in language teaching.

In Saudi Arabia, Osman (2015) investigated the teachers’ perception of intercultural communicative competence. Specifically, the study intended to determine the extent of teachers’ perception of intercultural communicative competence, the curriculum objectives that they deemed relevant and their teaching practices on integrating intercultural communicative competence. Accordingly, the respondents believed that the Intercultural Communicative Competence objectives were important or somewhat important in English language teaching. Similarly, they also manifested positive belief on the connection of the ICC objectives and the content of textbooks they use in the classroom. Moreover, most of the respondents claimed that they often present facts about the culture of English-speaking countries once they encounter them such as about food and greetings. However, there was a disagreement on the part of the participant as to how often the ICC objectives were practiced in the English classroom.

Using an exploratory investigation as a research approach, Israelsson (2016) investigated the perception of six EFL teachers on the concept of intercultural competence in teaching English. Findings revealed that the participants were not familiar with the concept. They generally considered intercultural competence as teaching values of different countries and how to react in different social

situations. Based on the interviews conducted, the participants seemed to have the understanding that intercultural communication is an alternative expression for cultural variety and a variety of cultural contexts. It was also found that only four of the five components of IC in Byram's model such as knowledge, skills to interpret, skills of discovery and interaction, and critical cultural awareness were reflected by the respondents. They did not manifest the attitude component of the IC model.

In the Turkish context, Saricoban and Oz (2014) explored the ICC level of pre-service English teachers including some factors that may influence the level of their ICC. Results showed that the participants manifested a high level of ICC in which knowledge component was the highest of the four components. As to the factors that affect ICC level, no significant difference was found between the male and female participants and their ICC level was not related at all to their academic achievement. However, ICC level was strongly correlated with studying abroad.

In the Philippines, Maure (2019) assessed the intercultural communicative competence of BSED major in English in a state university in northern Luzon. Using a survey questionnaire, findings revealed that the participants in the study were competent in their ICC considering their knowledge, skills, and attitude. They also manifested high level of competence along willingness to communicate. Significant relationships were yielded between the knowledge component of the participants' ICC and willingness to communicate, communication apprehension, and motivation. In addition, attitude component was also significantly related with willingness to communicate and motivation. However, the skill component of the participants ICC was found to have no significant relationship with willingness to communicate and communication apprehension.

Ang (2018) ventured on identifying knowledge, values, skills, behavior, and outcomes manifested in intercultural competence among 224 foreign and local students in a university in the Philippines. Results showed that the respondents were interested in intercultural competence. Moreover, they also showed high disposition toward it. Based on the findings, the university was able to create a model or framework of intercultural competence for global education.

Alaei and Nosrati (2018) investigated the Intercultural Communicative Competence and Intercultural Sensitivity levels of 167 Iranian EFL teachers. Results showed that the participants demonstrated a high level of ICC with the components of attitudes, skills and awareness as high while knowledge component was moderate. As regard their intercultural sensitivity, the participants' level was high in all components. In addition, the study also found that the knowledge component of ICC was significantly related with the components of IS such as interaction engagement, interaction confidence, and interaction attentiveness; however, no correlation was found with respecting cultural differences and interaction enjoyment. The attitude, skills and awareness components of ICC were correlated with all the components of IS.

Another study on intercultural sensitivity was conducted by Del Villar in the Philippines. Using a survey questionnaire, Del Villar (2012) examined the cultural sensitivity among 385 Filipinos from multinational corporations in the Philippines. Results revealed that Filipinos had high cultural sensitivity. In terms of relationship of the respondents' level of intercultural sensitivity with the three communication traits, it was found that cultural sensitivity correlated significantly with communication competence and willingness to communicate; however, it negatively correlated with communication apprehension. The respondents' intercultural sensitivity also correlated with some selected demographic variables such as age, years of membership in organizations, organizations in college, years spent in college organizations, number of business contacts, frequency of communication with business contacts, mode of communication with business contacts, number of countries visited, length of stay in another country/s, number of foreign friends, length of friendship, and frequency of communication with foreign friends. This finding implied that their demographic profile is influential in raising their intercultural sensitivity. Finally, intercultural sensitivity significantly correlated with all the components of the respondents' cultural orientation such as high context, low uncertainty reduction, collectivistic, high power distance, and masculinity.

Methodology

This research utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. Specifically, the identification of the beliefs and practices used mean and Standard Deviation and the identification of the relationship of the beliefs and practices and differences between the two groups used correlational measures.

The study was participated by the teachers of English subjects in the Senior High School of SMU, Bayombong with two males and seven females and the teachers of Purposive Communication in SMU with eight female English instructors. The seventeen participants were those who have taught the subject Oral Communication in the senior high school and Purposive Communication in the tertiary level. The other characteristics of the participants are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Profile of the Participants

Profile Variables		Tertiary	HS
Gender		8	
	Female	8	
	Male	0	
Age			
	20-30	0	
	31-40	2	
	41-50	2	
	51 above	4	
Years of teaching			
	1-5	0	
	6-10	0	
	11-15	2	
	16 and above	6	
Degree			
	Bachelor	2	
	Master	4	
	Doctor	2	
Courses taught			
a.	Undergraduate non-English major courses	3	
b.	Undergraduate English major courses	1	
c.	Graduate non-English major courses	0	
d.	Graduate English major courses	0	
e.	English courses in Senior High School	0	
f.	Undergraduate non-English major courses and Undergraduate English major courses	1	
g.	Undergraduate non-English major courses, Undergraduate English major courses and Graduate non-English major courses	1	
h.	Undergraduate non-English major courses, Undergraduate English major courses, Graduate non-English major courses and Graduate English major courses	0	
i.	Undergraduate non-English major courses, Undergraduate English major courses and Graduate English major courses	2	
j.	Undergraduate non-English major courses, Undergraduate English major courses, and English courses in Senior High School	0	
Academic Experience in other countries			
	Less than 6 months	4	
	6 months to 1 year	0	
	Above one year	0	
	No experience	4	

The primary tool used was a questionnaire that tried to identify the beliefs and practices of the participants regarding intercultural competence and how they teach it. The questionnaire (adapted from Tian, 2013) consists of five parts. The first part includes six statements regarding the respondents' beliefs about the importance of the objectives of English language teaching in the Philippines. The second part consists of 20 statements about the components of intercultural communication to determine which of these components are the most important or least important to be integrated in English language teaching. The third part includes six statements that would identify the teachers' beliefs in intercultural communication in the English language classroom. The fourth part includes items that would determine the teachers' practices in intercultural communication in the classroom. The first section consists of ten topics that the respondents need to identify frequency of integration in the classroom, and the second section includes eight statements about activities that are employed by the respondents whenever they address culture-related topics. The last part consists of five questions regarding the respondents' profile.

Written interview was conducted to the teachers to clarify some doubts in the participants' responses.

When approval to conduct the study has been sought, the teachers concerned were approached personally or via social media to get their consent to participate in the study. After getting the participants' consent, the questionnaires were distributed and retrieved immediately. The responses in the questionnaire were collated, encoded and analyzed.

Data were analyzed using mean and Standard deviation. The beliefs are measured based on what mentors believe as objectives of second language teaching, what they believe are components of intercultural competence for learners, and what they believe regarding intercultural competence in classroom teaching. These beliefs are measured on the following scale : strong belief (with a mean of 3.26-4.00), moderate belief (with a mean of 2.51-3.25), low belief (with a mean of 1.76-2.50) and lowest belief (with a mean of 1.00-1.75). The practices are measured according the topics they include in their lessons and the activities they use in their classes. These practices are measured on the following scale: high integration (mean=3.26-4.00), moderate integration (mean=2.51-3.25), low integration (mean=1.76-2.50) and lowest integration (mean=1.00-1.75) (Byram, 1997; Tian, 2013). Quantitative data were supported by qualitative data culled from the follow-up written interview.

Correlations of beliefs and practices were computed using Pearson-r and comparison of the ICCs of the two groups was computed using t-test.

Results and Discussion

Section 1. Beliefs of teachers/instructors/professors on Second Language Teaching (SLT) objectives, components of ICC

The mentors' mean scores in the questionnaire on their beliefs regarding the objectives of Second Language Teaching (SLT) range from 3.47 as shown in their *belief to increase the students' interest in learning a foreign language* to 3.88 as the highest for the three objectives in SLT. The scores show that the teachers' responses generally consider the objectives of SLT very

important. The objectives of Second Language Teaching related to intercultural communicative competence are considered very important for the respondents like developing a better understanding of students' own identity and culture, promoting the acquisition of an open mind and a positive attitude towards unfamiliar cultures, and promoting students' familiarity with the culture, civilization of the civilization of the countries where the foreign language is spoken. The following verbatim statements coming from the respondents reflect their beliefs regarding the importance of the objective components of ICC to SLT:

The world has indubitably become a global village. It is imperative that students are equipped with competence in intercultural communication so that they will be able to find their rightful niche in this ever-changing world (Respondent 1: tertiary level).

Intercultural Communication is an interesting subject to teach as it allows both teacher and learners to understand and appreciate linguistic creativity in multilingual situations across cultures (respondent 5: tertiary level).

Intercultural competence prepares us to deal better with intercultural differences (respondent 4: tertiary level).

The studies of Zhou (2011) and Nguyen (2015) support the finding of the present study in that their respondents considered the objectives of promoting intercultural competence of the students important. However, the study of Osman (2015) revealed that the objectives were found important or somewhat important by the respondents.

Figure 2 presents the objectives of SLT and the mean scores of the teachers/instructors/professors in the statements regarding SLT.

Figure 2. Mean scores of teachers/instructors/professors regarding the importance of SLT.
*The scores range from important to very important.

Section 2. Beliefs of teachers/instructors/professors on the components of ICC

Table 2 presents the mean scores of the two groups and in general as regards the teachers' beliefs on the components of ICC.

Table 2. Mean scores of the beliefs of teachers/instructors/professors on the components of ICC

Components of ICC	Overall Mean	Tertiary Mean	SHS Mean
1. Understanding others' worldviews	3.882	3.875	.89
2. Cultural self-knowledge	3.882	3.875	.89
3. Adaptability and adjustment to new cultural environment	4.000	4.000	.00
4. Skills to listen and observe	3.882	3.875	.89
5. Open attitude toward cross cultural learning and to people from other cultures	3.941	3.875	.00
6. Ability to adapt to different communication and learning styles	3.941	4.000	.89
7. Flexibility	4.000	4.000	.00
8. Skills to analyze, interpret, and relate	4.000	4.000	.00
9. Tolerating and engaging ambiguity	3.647	3.750	.56
10. Deep knowledge and understanding of culture (one's own and others')	3.941	3.875	.00
11. Respect for other cultures	4.000	4.000	.00
12. Understanding others' situation, feelings and motives	3.941	4.000	.89
13. Understanding the value of cultural diversity	4.000	4.000	.00
14. Understanding of role and impact of culture and the impact of situational, social, and historical contexts involved	4.000	4.000	.00
15. Cross-cultural awareness	3.882	4.000	.00
16. Withholding judgment	3.882	4.000	.00
17. Curiosity and discovery	4.000	3.875	.56
18. Learning through interaction	3.882	3.875	.00
19. Understanding from other's cultural frame of reference and cultural lens	3.941	3.875	.00
20. Culture-specific knowledge and understanding host culture's traditions among English learners in the Philippines.	3.941	3.875	.00

Table 2 shows that both groups of teachers generally consider the components of ICC as very important. In particular, the teacher respondents regard the following components as very important: adaptability and adjustment to new cultural environment; flexibility; skills to analyze, interpret and to relate; respect for other cultures; understanding the value of cultural diversity; understanding the role and impact of culture and the impact of situational, social, and historical contexts involve; and curiosity and discovery. The results signify that the respondents are more inclined to believe in the importance of the cognitive and skills components of Intercultural Communicative Competence. This finding contradicts that of Zhou (2011) where respondents considered the attitudinal components more important than knowledge components. On the other hand, Nguyen's study revealed that the respondents were more interested in the cultural knowledge and skills of learners than they were in the development of learners' attitudes.

Section 3. Beliefs of teachers/instructors/professors regarding ICC in classroom teaching

Figure 3 shows the mean scores of the teachers regarding ICC in classroom teaching.

Figure 3. Mean scores of teachers/instructors/professors' beliefs on ICC in classroom teaching

In general, the teachers consider the beliefs regarding ICC in the classroom important to very important. This implies that the development of learners' Intercultural Communicative Competence should be integrated in the English classrooms by the English language teachers. In particular, the teacher respondents strongly believe that English teachers should present a realistic image of foreign culture, and should touch upon positive and negative sides of the foreign culture and society; that they should focus on developing students' attitudes of openness and tolerance towards other peoples and cultures and that English teaching should touch upon both English and Philippine culture in order to help students to mediate between cultures. The results of the study on the teachers' beliefs are similar to the findings of Tian (2013) in which the participating teachers viewed various aspects of a person. In relation to the present study, attitude is most related.

The teachers' verbatim responses stated above also reflect their beliefs regarding the importance of ICC in the classroom. One respondent explicitly stated the following: Purposive Communication as a subject in college contains a unit in intercultural communicative competence. It bridges the gap that exists between and among different cultures, not only globally but also locally. I believe strongly that integrating ICC in the classroom is very relevant through Purposive Communication. For me, developing the learners' ICC is equally important as their English language proficiency (Respondent 2: tertiary).

Frequency of teachers' inclusion of the ICC topics and utilization of the ICC activities

Table 3. Mean frequency of teachers' inclusion of the ICC topics

Frequency of teachers' inclusion of the following topics in ICC	Overall Mean f	Tertiary Mean f	SHS Mean f
History, geography, and political conditions	2.647	2.625	2.67
Ethnic and social groups	3.176	3.25	3.11
Daily life and routines (food, drink and living condition, etc.)	3.000	3.25	2.78
Traditions, folklore, tourist attractions	2.941	3.00	2.89
Values and beliefs	3.059	3.25	2.89
Literature, music, theatre, film	3.000	3.125	2.89
Cultural differences	3.176	3.375	3.00
Educational systems	2.588	2.875	2.33
Religious beliefs	2.706	2.875	2.56
Technological development	2.882	3.375	2.44

* Overall mean: 3.1 (Teachers frequently, but not all the time integrate these topics in class.)

The teachers in general frequently integrate or include the ICC topics in their English class as shown in Table 3. However, topics like history, geography, and political conditions; traditions, folklore, tourist attractions, educational systems, religious beliefs, and technological development are not as frequently integrated as the other topics. This finding can be attributed to the

limitation of the content of the syllabus used by the college instructors and the curriculum guide used by the senior high school teacher. Osman's (2015) study found that the respondents included facts such as food or greetings of English-speaking countries. The respondents in the study of Chao (2016) preferred to integrate only the culture of the English native speakers.

Respondent 8 who teaches in the tertiary level usually integrate cultural differences in Purposive Communication as indicated in the following verbatim response:

One of the units in Purposive Communication is intercultural communication. It is in this part that I discuss cultural differences among Asian countries, specifically. Although I also touch cultural practices of Western countries, especially in their greetings.

One of the respondents claimed that she integrated cultural practices of both Western and Asian countries on food as presented in the following:

I do not only include cultural differences, but I also integrate daily routines of different countries, especially on food. I share to my students what I got from research in the internet the peoples table manners, as well as the reasons behind these practices.

Table 4. Mean frequency of teachers' utilization of the ICC activities

Activities in ICC	Overall Mean f	Tertiary Mean f	SHS Mean f
1. I tell students what I heard, read, or experienced about the foreign country or culture.	3.235	3.500	3.00
2. I use technology to illustrate a cultural topic.	2.882	2.875	2.89
3. I divide students into pairs or small groups to discuss or debate over a cultural topic.	2.941	3.125	2.78
4. I ask students to compare Philippine and English cultures regarding the topic.	2.882	3.250	2.56
5. I ask students to independently explore cultural events.	2.941	3.500	2.44
6. I ask students to explore cultural implications in teaching materials.	2.824	3.500	2.22
7. I ask students to explore areas of misunderstandings in communications between Filipinos and English-speaking people and explain the causes.	3.118	3.625	2.67
8. I ask students to explore values, beliefs and ideological perspectives implied in events/documents.	3.235	3.500	3.00

The teachers' overall mean of 3.75 shows that they almost always apply the eight ICC activities in class whenever they address culture-related topics. Teachers claim that they frequently tell students what they heard or experienced about the foreign country or culture; ask areas of misunderstandings in communications between Filipinos and English-speaking people and explain the causes; and ask students to explore values, beliefs and ideological perspectives implied in events/documents. Although with a lower mean, the teacher respondents also make use of technology to illustrate cultural topics; ask students to independently explore cultural events; ask students to compare Philippine and English cultures regarding the topic; and to explore cultural implications in teaching materials. The result coincides with that of Nguyen (2015) where teacher respondents used videos and internet to teach foreign cultures. However, the same finding contradicts that of Tian (2013) where respondents claimed that most of these activities were sometimes used by the respondents whenever they integrated ICC topics in their English classes.

In relation to the use of technology in integrating ICC related topics, one of the teacher respondents mentioned the following in the written interview:

Since technology plays a crucial role in education, this too can be a potential avenue for teaching ICC. Collaborative learning via ICT tools and Apps, film viewing (foreign or local) encourage students to explore and learn about others' cultures (Respondent 4: tertiary).

Another teacher respondent stated the following verbatim response in the written interview:

Videos are also utilized on the topics, 'Exploring Communication Situations Reflecting Different Cultures' and 'Coping with the Challenges of Intercultural Communication.' Students watch videos that show the distinct ways people from various racial groups speak English and they are asked to compare these to how most Filipinos speak the same language. A discussion on the reasons why people from different cultures do not speak the same way follows. Filipino English and other forms of Englishes are analyzed and interpreted. Cultural practices and customs are also given emphasis in this lesson. Here, students learn that practices, body language, facial expressions, and gestures that are common in the Philippines may not be acceptable in other countries. One activity that I usually require for this lesson is for students to research on how other people say basic phrases and sentences in their native language. The whole class also tries to pronounce the words, phrases,

and sentences the way the native speakers do. Again, watching and listening to videos provide a lot of help in this activity (Respondent 1: tertiary)

The same respondent mentioned the following as regards telling the students what she experienced in other countries and asking the students to do the same:

When it comes to dealing with foreign cultures, I often ask students who have lived or travelled abroad to share their experiences. I also share my encounters with foreigners during my travels as well as stories from my sisters who are based in the United States. I also emphasize the use of politically correct terms like for instance African-American for black people in the United States. One thing that I have learned from my readings and from my US-based siblings is that Negro or ‘Nigger’ are very offensive terms (Respondent 1: tertiary).

Respondent 4 who teaches in the tertiary level ask students to explore values, beliefs and ideological perspectives implied in events/documents as implied in the following verbatim response:

Moreover, to enrich our discussion, I shared to class my research papers on the phonological features of Philippine English varieties, food discourse and contrastive rhetoric for the different writing styles across nationalities and local ethnic groups (Respondent 4: tertiary).

Another respondents shared the following:

As an educator it is my responsibility to learn different cultures, language, norms, practices and multiplicities and how they (other cultures) come into play in different situations. I am doing this to be able to impart the knowledge to my students. I do this by showing my class documentaries, I ask them to listen to recordings of different languages, and let them watch videos. They also analyze cases and from there we discuss how their decisions were affected by their culture (Respondent 5, tertiary).

Correlation of Teachers’ Practices and Beliefs

Tables 5 and 6 show the beliefs that correlated with some ICC topics and ICC activities.

Table 5. Correlation of teachers’ beliefs regarding ICC and inclusion of topics

Inclusion of the Topic:	Teachers’ Beliefs regarding Intercultural Competence in Classroom Teaching That	
		Before you can do anything about the intercultural dimension of English teaching, the students have to possess a sufficiently high level of proficiency in English.
Daily life and routines (food, drink and living condition, etc.)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.643 (near strong negative rel’n) .005
Technological Development	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.496 (near moderate negative) .043
Cultural differences	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.566* (moderate negative) .018
Second Language Teachers’ Practices regarding Intercultural Competence in general	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.510* (moderate negative) .036

In general, the mentors believe that a sufficiently high proficiency in English is necessary before dealing with ICC. What is evident is that this belief resulted in varied negative relations with three topics in ICC such as daily life and routines, cultural differences, and technological development with second language teaching practices regarding ICC. The result implies that the more the teachers focus on English language proficiency, the less they take the topics for ICC. Based on the data, teachers in senior high school have higher mean score in relation to English proficiency as a requisite of intercultural communicative competence. This group of teachers have a strong belief that learners have to develop English language proficiency first before they can achieve a high level of intercultural communicative competence most especially on the aspects of daily life and routines, technological development, and cultural differences. The same finding is revealed in the study of Nguyen (2015) where the respondents showed more support to the development of the learners’ language competence than to the objective of developing intercultural competence. On the same line, Zhou (2011) found that although the respondents considered the objectives of promoting intercultural competence important, they regarded the linguistic dimension of teaching more important than cultural dimension.

If the teachers’ belief that the students have to possess a sufficiently high level of proficiency in English before they can develop intercultural competence in Table 5 correlated with some ICC

topics, in Table 6, the belief that English teaching should focus on developing students' attitudes of openness and tolerance towards other peoples and cultures correlated with some activities in ICC.

In general, the mentors believe that English teaching should focus on developing students' attitudes of openness and tolerance towards other peoples and cultures before dealing with the four activities in ICC such as asking the students to independently explore cultural events, areas of misunderstandings in communication, values, beliefs and ideological perspectives implied in events/documents, and second language teaching in general. What is evident is that this belief resulted in varied negative relations in the three ICC activities and with second language teaching activities regarding ICC. Hence, the more the teachers focus on developing students' attitudes of openness and tolerance towards other peoples and cultures, the less they conduct the said activities in ICC. This leaves a gray area for exploration as to what tasks the teachers give to develop attitudes of openness and tolerance towards other peoples and cultures.

Table 6. Correlation of teachers' beliefs regarding ICC and inclusion of activities

Inclusion of the Activity:	Teachers' Beliefs regarding Intercultural Competence in Classroom Teaching That English teaching should focus on developing students' attitudes of openness and tolerance towards other peoples and cultures.	
I ask students to independently explore cultural events.	Pearson Correlation Sig.(2-tailed)	-.611** (moderate negative rel'n) .009
I ask students to explore areas of misunderstandings in communications between Filipinos and English-speaking people and explain the causes. Cultural differences	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.491 (near moderate negative) .045
I ask students to explore values, beliefs and ideological perspectives implied in events/documents.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.485* (near moderate negative) .049
Second Language Teachers' Activities regarding ICC in general	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.511* (moderate negative) .036

Beliefs and Practices in ICC in Relation to Profile

Table 7. Correlation of ICC activities and respondents' profile: age

ICC Activities	Teachers' Age	
I tell students what I heard, read, or experienced about the foreign country or culture.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.508* (moderate strong positive association) .037
I ask students to explore cultural implications in teaching materials.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.628** (near strong positive association) .007

Table 7 shows that the older the teacher becomes, the more frequent the teacher uses the ICC activities specifically in telling what he/she heard, read or experienced about foreign country or culture and in asking students to explore cultural implications in teaching materials. As indicated in the data, most teachers in the tertiary level whose age are older indicated to have at least experiences in other countries. Hence, they are the ones who frequently tell what they hear/heard or experienced about foreign country or culture. The following are the verbatim responses of the teachers in their written interview:

I also share my encounters with foreigners during my travels as well as stories from my sisters who are based in the United States (Respondent 1: tertiary: age: beyond 50) Whenever the situation allows it, I share to my students what I experienced in other countries like Indonesia,

Thailand, Malaysia, and Belgium. I share them my experiences to familiarize them with the practices of these countries which may differ from what we have in the Philippines (Respondent 2: tertiary: age: beyond 50)

Table 8. Correlation of ICC activities and respondents' profile: gender

ICC Activities		Teachers' Gender
I ask students to explore areas of misunderstandings in communications between Filipinos and English-speaking people and explain the causes.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.491* (near moderate negative association) .046

Table 8 shows that the female teachers (designated with the numerical point of 1) tend to utilize the ICC activity of asking students to explore areas of misunderstandings in communications between Filipinos and English-speaking people and explain the causes more frequently than the males (assigned the numerical point of 2). In relation to gender or sex classification, it must be noted that the number of the females far outweighs the number of the males. Hence, the findings need more validation as regards gender.

Table 9. Correlation of ICC activities and respondents' profile: years of teaching

ICC Activities		Teachers' Years of Teaching
I ask students to explore areas of misunderstandings in communications between Filipinos and English-speaking people and explain the causes.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.499* (near moderate negative association) .041

The longer the teaching experience of the teacher, the more frequent he/she asks his/her students to explore areas of misunderstandings in communications between Filipinos and English-speaking people and lets them explain the causes. As far as experience is concerned, teachers in the tertiary level have longer experience in teaching than those in the senior high school. Moreover, most of the teachers in the tertiary level have more exposure on the phenomenon of World Englishes in which topics related to communication in the different varieties of English are discussed. Hence, these teachers are the ones who employ the activity of asking students to explore areas of misunderstandings in communications between Filipinos and English-speaking people and explain the causes. They integrate examples of linguistic features that may cause misunderstanding between speakers based on research.

Difference Between the SHS and Tertiary Groups in ICC Beliefs and Practices

Table 9. Differences between the SHS and tertiary groups in ICC beliefs and practices

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-Test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower		Upper
English teaching should focus on developing students' attitudes of openness and tolerance towards other peoples and cultures.	Equal variances assumed	119.118	.000	-2.183	15	.045	-.3750	.1718	-.7412	-.0088
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.049	7.000	.080	-.3750	.1830	-.8077	.0577

Among the variables, the two groups are found significantly different only in the belief that *English teaching should focus on developing students' attitudes of openness and tolerance towards other peoples and*

cultures in which the SHS teachers gained a higher mean. This shows that though both groups agree that developing tolerance and openness among the students is important, the SHS were more convinced of its importance. This could be attributed to the level of the students, their culture as part of the Basic Education and as teenagers as claimed by their teachers and to the fact that they are more governed by the Curriculum Guide provided by the Department of Education. However, these needs further verification.

This study acknowledges its limitations as to the number of respondents who participated to arrive at a more conclusive results. It further presents the scarce sources on ICC studies in the language classroom and to the subjects in the Philippine government as a product of the K12 curriculum. Hence, this study is a seminal paper. This study on beliefs and practices of tertiary and SHS teachers regarding Intercultural Communicative Competence is an eye-opener to all English language teachers as regards the relevance of Intercultural Communicative Competence to both teachers and learners. The beliefs and practices of the teachers on ICC are reflected in their teaching English to students; thereby, the learners' ICC may also be influenced. The English teachers of SMU in both levels are compliant to the integration of intercultural communicative competence as one aspect of 21st century learners' communication skills. The SHS teachers believe that their students need more enhancement of intercultural tolerance and openness. Moreover, English language proficiency is seen to be relevant in developing ICC. Since Saint Mary's University is a multicultural institution where students of varied cultures interact, Intercultural Communicative Competence is imperative. After all, ICC does not only include cultures of people from other countries but also the local cultures in our own community and country. It is therefore recommended to conduct a seminar-workshop for the two groups of respondents on Intercultural Communicative Competence, especially on topics to be included in the English classes as well as the activities to be employed in integrating varied topics on Intercultural Communicative Competence.

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Dear Sir/Madam,

Greetings of peace!

We are faculty members from the School of Teachers Education and Humanities (STEH) conducting a research on the beliefs and practices of English teachers on intercultural competence. In this line, we appeal for your support and active participation as the results will imply pedagogical implications. Rest assured that all data gathered will be treated with utmost confidentiality and will be used for the purposes of this research only.

Thank you very much for your cooperation and support!

Very truly yours,

Researchers

SURVEY ON TEACHERS' BELIEFS OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE
COMPETENCE IN SECOND LANGUAGE TEACHING
(Adapted from Tian, 2013)

Objectives of Second Language Teaching.

Six possible objectives of second language teaching have been listed below. Please circle the number that shows the importance of each of them in your opinion. Number "1" indicates the objective which you consider Not Important, "2" Somewhat Important, "3" Important, and "4" Very Important.

Objectives of Second Language Teaching	Not Important	Somewhat Important	Important	Very Important
1. Increase students' interest in learning a foreign language	1	2	3	4
2. Promote students' familiarity with the culture, the civilization of the countries where the foreign language which they are learning is spoken.	1	2	3	4
3. Assist students to acquire a level of proficiency in the foreign language that will allow them to read literary works in the foreign language.	1	2	3	4
4. Assist students to acquire skills that will be useful in other subject areas and in real life (such as memorize, summarize, give a presentation, etc.).	1	2	3	4
5. Promote the acquisition of an open mind and a positive attitude towards unfamiliar cultures.	1	2	3	4
6. Assist students in developing a better understanding of their own identity and culture.	1	2	3	4

A. Components of Intercultural Competence for Language Learners in the Philippines

Items	Not Important	Somewhat Important	Important	Very Important
1. Understanding others' worldviews	1	2	3	4
2. Cultural self-knowledge	1	2	3	4
3. Adaptability and adjustment to new cultural environment	1	2	3	4

4. Skills to listen and observe	1	2	3	4
5. Open attitude toward cross-cultural learning and to people from other cultures	1	2	3	4
6. Ability to adapt to different communication and learning styles	1	2	3	4
7. Flexibility	1	2	3	4
8. Skills to analyze, interpret, and relate	1	2	3	4
9. Tolerating and engaging ambiguity	1	2	3	4
10. Deep knowledge and understanding of culture (one's own and others')	1	2	3	4
11. Respect for other cultures	1	2	3	4
12. Understanding others' situation, feelings and motives	1	2	3	4
13. Understanding the value of cultural diversity	1	2	3	4
14. Understanding of role and impact of culture and the impact of situational, social, and historical contexts involved	1	2	3	4
15. Cross-cultural awareness	1	2	3	4
16. Withholding judgment	1	2	3	4
17. Curiosity and discovery	1	2	3	4
18. Learning through interaction	1	2	3	4
19. Understanding from other's cultural frame of reference and cultural lens	1	2	3	4
20. Culture-specific knowledge and understanding host culture's traditions among English learners in the Philippines.	1	2	3	4

The following twenty items have been mentioned in different literature as components of intercultural competence for English language learners. Please circle the number that shows the importance of each of them in your opinion to the development of intercultural competence

B. Teachers' Beliefs regarding Intercultural Competence in Classroom Teaching. Circle a response that best represents your opinion.

Beliefs	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
1. Based on your experience, English language and its culture can be taught in an integrated way.	1	2	3	4
2. Before you can do anything about the intercultural dimension of English teaching, the students have to possess a sufficiently high level of proficiency in English.	1	2	3	4
3. English teaching should touch upon both English and Philippine culture in order to help students to mediate between the two cultures.	1	2	3	4
4. Besides British and American cultures, English teachers should also touch upon cultures of other English-speaking countries.	1	2	3	4
5. English teaching should focus on developing students' attitudes of openness and tolerance towards other peoples and cultures.	1	2	3	4
6. English teachers should present a realistic image of a foreign culture, and therefore should touch upon both positive and negative sides of the foreign culture and society.	1	2	3	4

C. Second Language Teachers' Practices regarding Intercultural Competence

D.1. In your teaching, how often do you touch upon the following topics?

Topics	Never	Sometimes	Frequently	Always
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1. History, geography, and political conditions	1	2	3	4
2. Ethnic and social groups	1	2	3	4
3. Daily life and routines (food, drink and living condition, etc.)	1	2	3	4
4. Traditions, folklore, tourist attractions	1	2	3	4
5. Values and beliefs	1	2	3	4
6. Literature, music, theatre, film	1	2	3	4
7. Cultural differences	1	2	3	4
8. Educational systems	1	2	3	4
9. Religious beliefs	1	2	3	4
10. Technological development	1	2	3	4

D.2 How often do you apply the following activities when you address culture-related topics in your English class? (Circle the corresponding answer).

Activities	Never	Sometimes	Frequently	Always
1. I tell students what I heard, read, or experienced about the foreign country or culture.	1	2	3	4
2. I use technology to illustrate a cultural topic.	1	2	3	4
3. I divide students into pairs or small groups to discuss or debate over a cultural topic.	1	2	3	4
4. I ask students to compare Philippine and English cultures regarding the topic.	1	2	3	4
5. I ask students to independently explore cultural events.	1	2	3	4
6. I ask students to explore cultural implications in teaching materials.	1	2	3	4
7. I ask students to explore areas of misunderstandings in communications between Filipinos and English-speaking people and explain the causes.	1	2	3	4
8. I ask students to explore values, beliefs and ideological perspectives implied in events/documents.	1	2	3	4

Background Information. Kindly put a check and/or fill in the necessary information asked in each of the following items.

1. Your gender Female Male
2. Your age _____ Birthday month _____ day _____ year _____
3. Years of teaching (total) _____ In SMU only _____ In English _____
4. Your highest degree (a) Bachelor (b) Master (c) Doctorate
5. Please check type(s) of the courses you teach (you may respond to more than one answer.)
 (a) Undergraduate non-English major courses
 (b) Undergraduate English major courses
 (c) Graduate non-English major courses
 (d) Graduate English major courses
 (e) English courses in Senior High School
6. Your experiences in **other countries** (Please check the type and indicate the country below each; write the length of time the experience lasted):

Experience type	<input type="checkbox"/> teaching	<input type="checkbox"/> training	<input type="checkbox"/> research	<input type="checkbox"/> study
Country				
Duration/length				

Others, please specify using this space

APPENDIX B: CONSENT FORM

Dear colleagues in this institution,

We, the undersigned, are faculty members of STEH in Saint Mary's University and are currently conducting a research on intercultural competence. In this line, we appeal for your support and participation by answering the questionnaire honestly and completely. Rest assured that any information taken from your responses will not in any way harm you since they will be handled with care and utmost confidentiality; the data will be used only for this study.

If at any time you would like additional information about our study, you can contact us at mbquerol@yahoo.com or zjasuncion@yahoo.com. **Your signature below indicates that you have given your informed consent to participate.**

We will forever be grateful of your kindness and participation.

Thank you very much. God bless.

The researchers,

MS. ZAYDA S. ASUNCION

MS. MARITES B. QUEROL

MRS. INES R. MINIA

MRS. ROSALIE L. NAVOA

Consent

I have understood the purpose and nature of the study. I give my consent to participate in this study.

Participant's signature _____

Date: _____